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HARNESSING MICROBIOMES FOR ENHANCED BIOREMEDIATION: Insights from the MIBIREM and BIOSYSMO Joint meeting

Date: 19-20 March 2025

A two-day joint meeting between the **MIBIREM** and **BIOSYSMO** projects was held to foster collaboration, share progress, and address common challenges in advancing bioremediation as a standalone solution for environmental pollution. Funded under the Horizon Europe framework, both projects aim to harness the potential of microbiomes for the sustainable remediation of contaminated environments.

Participants from both projects presented case studies, emerging technologies, and integration strategies that highlighted the strong synergies between BIOSYSMO and MIBIREM. A key focus was the development and application of advanced microbial consortia, multi-omics approaches, and systems biology to enhance the predictability and robustness of microbial remediation. The discussions also emphasized mutual efforts to design decision-support systems, strengthen stakeholder engagement, and align bioremediation practices with policy frameworks across the EU.

Shared advancements and cooperation

Opening remarks by Sara Gil Guerrero (IDENER, BIOSYSMO Project Coordinator) and David Donnerer (RTDS Association, MIBIREM Project Manager) set the tone for two days of structured exchange. In their opening dialogue, the coordinators highlighted the importance of building on the collaboration agreement signed between both consortia and framing the joint meeting as an opportunity for structured integration, rather than a mere exchange of updates.

An overview session led by Sara Gil Guerrero and Thomas Reichenauer (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH, MIBIREM Scientific Coordinator) offered comparative insights into project scopes, progress,

and key challenges. This was followed by a flash presentation session from the representative partners, where **MIBIREM** presented five core enabling technologies, while **BIOSYSMO** showcased five applied case studies. The format highlighted the complementarity of the projects, from the design of microbial systems to their deployment in real-world scenarios.

A major takeaway was the importance of advancing digital tool development. In this regard, BIOSYSMO is focused on computational design and systems-level modelling of microbial solutions, while MIBIREM is oriented toward field implementation and site-specific optimisation. Together, these strengths offer a foundation for the co-development of decision-support systems that integrate biological, chemical, and environmental data.

In line with this, the session also explored the **potential establishment of a shared repository** for microbial consortia and multi-omics data. Such a platform could support standardisation, ensure reproducibility, and enhance interoperability between datasets and models. This proposal aligns with BIOSYSMO's systems biology ambitions and MIBIREM's applied, field-focused approach. Both consortia agreed on the importance of jointly exploring its technical, legal, and operational feasibility.

Field studies and real-world validation

In a session dedicated to field studies, presented by Alfredo Pérez de Mora (TAUW, BIOSYSMO field studies lead), Jessica Beyert (SENSATEC GmbH, MIBIREM field studies lead), and Cosimo Masini (DND Biotech, MIBIREM), the critical role of testing microbial strategies under realistic

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conditions was reinforced. The presenters shared updates on the status of field trials, TRL levels, and challenges related to scalability, heterogeneity, and engineering constraints.

Case studies covered a diverse range of environmental matrices and contaminants. A dedicated discussion block focused on the transition from lab to field via mesocosm testing, emphasising the need to safeguard microbial viability and system performance across complex ecosystems.

The HCH Case Study: A focal point for Joint Collaboration

The second day was centred on the **shared Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) case study**, featuring contributions from **Rocío Barros García** (University of Burgos, BIOSYSMO HCH lead), **Simona Di Gregorio** and **Giacomo Bernabei** (University of Pisa, MIBIREM HCH lead), and others. The session showcased a coordinated effort to investigate degradation pathways and evaluate microbial performance across contaminated sites in Spain, Italy, and Germany.

The case study discussion included insights into experimental work being conducted at the **Sabiñánigo** site in Spain, a legacy industrial location with well-documented historical HCH pollution. Contributions from the University of Burgos provided an overview of local site characteristics and microbial enrichment strategies followed, while the University of Pisa outlined complementary work on HCH-affected sites in Italy and Germany. Both universities highlighted the work developed focused on microbial selection, community stability, and performance evaluation in site-specific conditions. In parallel, **Alez Lapanje** (Jožef Stefan Institute, BIOSYSMO) shared developments in microbial immobilisation and surface modification techniques aimed at enhancing biofilm formation and microbial stability post-deployment aligned with the main challenges of the project. Additional contributions came from **Zheren Zhang** and **José Jiménez** (Imperial College London, BIOSYSMO), where ongoing work supports the genetic characterisation and engineered functions.

The discussion highlighted performance losses after cryopreservation, the promise of immobilisation techniques, and the integration of genomic and culturomics data to design more effective microbial consortia. **Joni Elsmoortel** and **Peter Vandamme** (University of Ghent,

MIBIREM) contributed to insights into microbiome preservation. The session also emphasised the added value of combining multi-omics data (e.g. metagenomics and metatranscriptomics) with genome-scale metabolic models, such as the community models developed by **Akanksha Mishra** (IDENER, BIOSYSMO), to better understand microbial community function and optimise synthetic consortia.

Regulatory considerations and harmonisation needs

Participants highlighted the ongoing regulatory challenges faced by both consortia. BIOSYSMO continues to face constraints in field testing of genetically modified organisms, while MIBIREM needs to establish robust performance benchmarks for degrading microbiomes and is also navigating how best to communicate risk levels associated with naturally derived microbiomes. There was broad agreement on the need for standardised qPCR primer sets, harmonised monitoring protocols, and stronger science-policy dialogue. Cross-project learning in this area is seen as essential for accelerating regulatory acceptance and enabling broader deployment of microbiome-based remediation strategies.

In closing, the joint meeting reinforced the mutual benefits of continued integration between BIOSYSMO and MIBIREM. Both projects expressed commitment to long-term cooperation in data exchange, toolkit development, and regulatory alignment, laying the groundwork for positioning microbiome-based bioremediation as a credible and scalable solution within the European environmental policy framework.

Next Actions

As a result of the discussions, several **next steps** were proposed:

- Continue exchanging and analysing multi-omics data, with joint activities focused on the HCH case and opportunities for cross-site comparisons.
- Plan practical training sessions and workshops to support knowledge exchange on technical topics relevant to both projects (e.g., microbial immobilisation, modelling platforms, or field protocols).
- Explore the potential establishment of a shared repository for microbial consortia and multi-omics data, and support alignment of protocols and formats.
- Identify common regulatory concerns and prepare to contribute to relevant discussions at EU level, especially around microbiome use and risk communication.